

ANALYSIS OF HYDRO-PNEUMATIC SUSPENSION SYSTEM FOR RALLY TRUCK AND TO CHECK ITS FEASIBILITY FOR COMMERCIAL DELIVERY VANS

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ABSTRACT:

The suspension system is the main part of the vehicle, where the shock absorber is designed mechanically to handle shock impulse and dissipate kinetic energy. The basic study of hydro pneumatic suspension system is carried out for GINAF rally truck which has been as a part of this project to get a basic idea regarding the system and applicability in commercial vans. As spring is basic element of any suspension system, study and analysis of the spring is carried out. Optimization of the spring for the generalized suspension is done and checked in modal as well as structural analysis in ANSYS. And found that the newly designed spring is feasible for Conventional as well hydro pneumatic suspension system. Applicability of this newly designed hydro pneumatic suspension is checked for Indian commercial delivery vehicle and stresses are found way under the maximum failure limit. Feasibility of hydro pneumatic suspension system including all the requirements has been checked in this project against wear, bumping etc. Also Feasibility of the whole system has been checked for front as well as rear wheels differently and found suitable.

I INTRODUCTION:

Passive suspension systems (suspensions with no controllable elements) always lead to a compromise between ride comfort and handling, since a stiff suspension is required for good handling, while a more compliant suspension improves ride comfort. Implementing a controllable suspension is therefore an attempt to deal with these opposing requirements for improved ride comfort and handling by providing the opportunity to adjust incorporating the applicable criteria that follow. The semi-active suspension system used in current practice is shown in Figure 1. it works as follows: The switching between high and low characteristics for both the spring and the damper characteristics is made possible by redirecting the hydraulic fluid with two solenoid valves. The spring/damper unit consists of a hydraulic strut, two Nitrogen filled accumulators and hydraulic damper and the two solenoid valves. The low

spring rate is achieved by compressing a large volume of gas, consisting of two separate accumulators. By closing off one of the accumulators, a smaller gas volume is compressed and hence a higher spring rate is achieved. Spring rates can be individually tailored by changing the two gas volumes when the system is designed. [1]

In order to analyze the behavior of the vehicle using an active suspension system, it is easier to make a model first and to perform simulations using the control system for the active suspension. Therefore this simulation model should not only represent the overall vehicle behavior accurately but also has to represent the suspension components well.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The main objective to carry out this project work is to develop a simulation model containing the hydro-pneumatic suspension system of Rally Truck. The model is validated by measurement data on both component level as well as full vehicle level. The model can be used for further research with respect to active damping control or implementing the system in other groups of vehicles like commercial delivery vans.

The purpose of this project was to determine the following parts:

- I. To Study Basics of hydro-pneumatic suspension system.
- II. To Study & Design hydro-pneumatic suspension system for Rally Truck.
- III. To do preliminary simulation by hydro-pneumatic suspension system.

- IV. To optimize parameters of hydro-pneumatic suspension system
- V. To simulate the optimized parameters.
- VI. To check feasibility for commercial delivery van's suspension system.

III. ANALYSIS OF HYDRO-PNEUMATIC SUSPENSION SYSTEM USING ANSYS:

ANSYS is finite element analysis software which enables engineers to perform the following tasks:

- The solid model of rail-wheel contact model is created in CATIA V5. It is a feature based modeling (FBM) software. Many CAD packages use FBM method. It is easy and gives model tree for completed part, so that modification at any point at any branch can be passed through whole model.

Fig: CAD model of Hydro-pneumatic suspension system

- The CAD model of rail-wheel contact was saved in .igs format for importing it into ANSYS workbench for the analysis purpose.
- Meshing is the process in which your geometry is discretized into elements and nodes. This mesh along with material properties is used to mathematically represent the stiffness and mass distribution of the structure. The element size is determined based on number of factors including overall model size, body curvature and the complexity of the feature.

Fig: Meshing of Hydro-pneumatic suspension system

- The boundary condition is the collection of different forces, pressure, velocity, supports, constraints and every condition required for complete analysis. Applying boundary condition is one of the most typical processes of analysis.

Fig: Loading & Boundary Condition

- In structural analysis, after specification of meshing, material properties, boundary conditions and application of loads, solution is obtained in terms of deflection & von-mises stress

Fig: Deflection in suspension System

Fig: Von-mises Stresses in suspension system

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

After giving the loading conditions as per theoretical iterations following results are obtained from ANSYS

Sr.no	Load (N)	Von-mises Stress MPa	Deflection (δ) mm
1	850	170.56	9.00
2	1100	225.86	11.58
3	1500	342.41	17.50
4	1900	450.21	23.14
5	2300	560.52	30.59

V. CONCLUSION:

In this project we have designed a hydro pneumatic suspension system for commercial transport vans in India. Conclusions for the project are as follows.

- i. The basic study of hydro pneumatic suspension system is carried out for GINAF rally truck has been carried out as a part of this project to get a basic idea regarding the system and applicability in commercial vans.

- ii. As spring is basic element of any suspension system, study and analysis of the spring is carried out. Optimization of the spring for the generalized suspension is done and checked in modal as well as structural analysis in ANSYS. And found that the newly designed spring is feasible for Conventional as well hydro pneumatic suspension system.
- iii. Applicability of this newly designed hydro pneumatic suspension is checked for Indian commercial delivery vehicle and stresses are found way under the maximum failure limit. So it can be concluded that this suspension can be used in concern with stress and failure.
- iv. Feasibility of hydro pneumatic suspension system including all the requirements has been checked in this project against wear, bumping etc. Also Feasibility of the whole system has been checked for front as well as rear wheels differently and found suitable.
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